

The study of malate dehydrogenases with oxidoreductase and decarboxylase activity in bread wheat genotypes

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The important and complex role of NADP-MDH and NADP-ME indicates their necessity in carbon and energy distribution in higher plants. This requires the introduction of new ideas about the biochemical and molecular mechanisms connecting respiration, photosynthesis, and photorespiration in plants. Therefore, the activity of the main enzymes of malate metabolism – NADP-malate dehydrogenase (NADP-MDH) and NADP-malic enzyme (NADP-ME), and Relative Water Content (RWC) were studied in the leaves of bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) genotypes that belong to the C3 pathway of photosynthesis and differ in drought tolerance. The highest NADP-MDH activity was detected in the genotypes Murov 2 and Zirva 85. RWC was highest in Murov 2 and Aran genotypes, and lower in the Gyzyly bughda genotype compared to others. Thus, the research revealed that the Murov 2 genotype can be cultivated in rainfed and semi-arid regions, and can be used as a starting material for creating stress-tolerant wheat varieties in practical breeding programs.

Keywords: Drought stress, malate metabolism, NADP-MDH, NADP-ME

INTRODUCTION

In addition to being a period of economic growth, the 21st century also plays an important role in increasing the productivity of cultivated species as a period of intensive study of metabolic processes in plants and the development of methodology in plant research (Nagy and Garab 2021, Adamidis et al., 2019; Simkin et al., 2019; Yan et al., 2022; Brestic et al., 2021). In the globalized world, the rapid increase in population, the decrease in biodiversity, and the limitation of suitable and productive land areas for agriculture pose a serious threat to meeting people's food needs (Ghatak et al., 2022). In this regard, the direct or indirect effect of abiotic stress factors, including drought, on photosynthesis remains a subject of active discussions among scientists in this field during recent decades (Chen et al., 2019; Kapoor et al., 2020).

Wheat is an important food product in the world and constitutes 18-20% of human dietary protein (Padhan et al., 2020). In this respect, the study of malate dehydrogenase system enzymes with oxidoreductase and decarboxylase activity, which play an important role in increasing productivity in wheat plants, is important (Singh et al 2022). The enzyme NADP-ME reduces NAD(P)⁺ to NAD(P)H in the oxidative

decarboxylation of L-malate (MAL) to pyruvate (PYR) (Hsieh et al., 2019; Sarkar et al., 2020). NADP-malic enzyme participates in numerous metabolic processes and plays an important role in plant tolerance to various stress factors (Shao et al., 2011). It is known that stress factors such as drought, salinity, and cold affect the entire metabolism by impairing the development of plants. Being a product of the reaction catalyzed by NADP-ME, NADPH as one of the main factors determining cell development is involved in the biosynthesis of osmotically active substances such as proline, mannose-6-phosphate, and mannitol. Stress affects the water balance, leading to loss of turgor and membrane breakdown. This condition caused by stress in the plant cell requires the regeneration of membrane lipids. NADP-ME participates in the regeneration process by directing pyruvate and NADPH to the biosynthesis of fatty acids (Sun et al., 2019).

The NADP-MDH enzyme converts oxaloacetate into malate using excess NADPH to regenerate the NADP electron acceptor (Yokochi et al., 2021). The activity level of the enzyme is higher in the young leaves of the plant and decreases as the leaves age. This fact indicates that the enzymatic activity of NADP-MDH is closely related to active metabolism. The activation of NADP-MDH is inhibited by its product, NADP.

Therefore, when NADPH is used for assimilation processes in the chloroplast, NADP-MDH "turns off" its activity. Due to this, the export of reducing equivalents such as malate does not occur. Because ATP formation continues as electrons are transferred to malate, the malate valve plays a crucial role in maintaining the ATP/NADPH balance in chloroplasts as an indirect export system of reducing equivalents (Selinski and Scheibe, 2019; Elsässer et al., 2020).

The study of the regulation mechanisms of metabolic processes creates conditions for understanding the biochemical mechanisms of plant adaptation to stress. From this point of view, the study of malate dehydrogenases and malic enzymes in the active stages of plant development is of particular importance. The study of the effect of soil drought on plant organisms is still of great theoretical and practical importance as an important scientific direction and opens wide prospects for the creation of plant varieties tolerant to unfavorable external environmental factors.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The genotypes stored in the wheat gene pool of the Research Institute of Crop Husbandry of the Ministry of Agriculture were compared and 4 genotypes were selected: Murov 2, Aran, Gyzył bughda, and Zirva 85. Bread wheat genotypes were cultivated in an artificial climate laboratory with a light period of 16/8 hours, 50% relative humidity, and a temperature regime of 24°C/18°C day/night, respectively. Drought stress was applied to 14-day-old seedlings. Measurements were made in 10 biological and 3 technical replicates in 2 variants.

NADP-MDH activity assay: The determination of the NADP-MDH activity started with the activation of the enzyme. Activation was performed for 15 minutes using 1 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0) containing 10 mg/ml BSA, 100 mM DTT, and the enzyme preparation. The reaction medium for NADP-MDH was as follows: 100 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0), 10 mg/ml BSA, 0.5 M EDTA·4Na, 20 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM NADP·H, and 30 µl activated enzyme preparation. The reaction started by adding 10 µl of 1 mM OA to the reaction medium. The determination of the enzyme activity is based on the decline in optical density for 1 min of the reaction course due to the expenditure of NADPH. The millimolar equivalent of ε-extinction for NADPH at maximum absorption amounted to 6.22 mM·cm⁻¹ at 340 nm (Keryer et al., 2004).

NADP-ME activity assay: The enzyme activity was determined based on an increase in the optical density due to the formation of NADPH. The reaction medium for the determination was as

follows: 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.2), 1 mM EDTA·4Na, 20 mM MgCl₂, 0.5 mM NADP⁺, 5 mM L-malate·Na, and the enzyme extraction. The reaction started by adding malate to the reaction medium (Voll et al., 2012).

Relative Water Content (RWC) of the leaves was measured using the Turner method (Turner, 1981). The leaves were kept in distilled water. After the determination of the turgor weight, leaves were placed in the thermostat (80°C) and weighed again after obtaining constant weight. RWC was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{RWC} = [(\text{FW} - \text{DW}) / (\text{TW} - \text{DW})] \cdot 100$$

where: FW- fresh weight, TW- turgor weight, DW- dry weight.

Protein was measured by the method of Rekowski, using bovine serum albumin as the standard (Rekowski, 2021).

The significance of differences between mean values was compared by Student's t-test. Differences at $P \leq 0.05$ were considered significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NADP-MDH is redox-regulated, activated by light and it is inactive in the dark. NADP-MDH localized in chloroplasts plays an important role in maintaining a balance of reduced equivalents between cytosol and stroma. Considering this, we determined the NADP-MDH activity in irrigated and drought-exposed variants of chosen wheat genotypes.

The highest NADP-MDH activity was observed in the genotypes Murov 2 and Zirva 85. The enzyme activity changed similarly in the leaves of irrigation and drought variants. The enzyme activity decreased gradually in the leaves of the drought-exposed Gyzył bughda genotype. The responses of plants to water stress differ depending on the plant species, the type of organ and tissue, the compartmentalization of the cell, the intensity and duration of water deficit, and the stage of ontogenesis (Rampino et al., 2006; Yang et al., 2010; Aranjuelo et al., 2012).

Compared to the results obtained on the 2nd day of the drought, after four and six days of irrigation, the enzyme activity increased by 40.0% and 57.2%, respectively in the leaves of the Murov 2 genotype. During the first four days of drought, in the leaves of the Zirva 85 genotype, the NADP-MDH activity changed similarly in the irrigated and drought variants. In the leaves of the Gyzył bughda genotype, the enzyme activity decreased gradually under drought (Table 1). The gradual decrease in the (Babayev et al., 2015).

Table 1. Dynamics of NADP-MDH activity changes in wheat leaves

Genotypes	Variants	NADP-MDH activity, EU/mg protein				
		Drought days				
		2	4	6	8	10
Murov 2	irrigation	15.69±1.4	16.71±1.7	17.9±2.0	18.71±1.7	18.9±2.0
	drought	13.04±1.3 ^{ns}	18.3±2.0*	20.5±2.1**	21.7±2.3**	18.9±1.8*
Zirva 85	irrigation	18.71±1.4	18.9±2.2	20.71±1.7	24.9±2.7	22.0±2.3
	drought	17.33±1.5*	19.1±2.0**	25.71±1.7*	24.9±2.5**	15.9±1.3*
Aran	irrigation	8.51±0.8	8.9±0.6	10.8±1.2	14.9±1.3	15.9±1.5
	drought	7.1±0.7 ^{ns}	7.9±0.9*	8.7±1.0*	7.9±0.6*	6.7±0.4*
Gyzyl bughda	irrigation	13.1±1.8	18.9±1.6	19.8±1.9	24.9±2.3	16.9±1.5
	drought	13.1±1.9**	13.9±1.1*	13.7±1.3*	11.9±1.1*	4.7±0.1 ^{ns}

Results of Student's *t* – test **,* – significance at the 0.01, 0.05 probability levels, respectively

Table 2. Dynamics of changes in NADP-ME activity in wheat leaves

Genotypes	Variants	NADP-ME activity EU/mg protein				
		Drought days				
		2	4	6	8	10
Murov 2	irrigation	1.38±0.12	1.76±0.18	1.88±0.12	2.27±0.12	2.68±0.12
	drought	1.24±0.14*	1.54±0.16*	1.68±0.19 ^{ns}	2.54±0.25 ^{ns}	3.14±0.36*
Zirva 85	irrigation	1.18±0.1	1.3±0.02	1.45±0.15	1.5±0.16	1.8±0.2
	drought	1.54±0.18*	1.7±0.2*	2.45±0.15*	3.5±0.35*	2.3±0.1 ^{ns}
Aran	irrigation	0.28±0.02	0.8±0.01	0.84±0.07	1.24±0.05	1.36±0.05
	drought	0.24±0.02 ^{ns}	0.44±0.02*	0.52±0.02*	0.4±0.05*	0.76±0.05*
Gyzyl bughda	irrigation	0.31±0.04	0.34±0.04	0.44±0.04	0.74±0.05	1.48±0.05
	drought	0.24±0.05*	0.36±0.05 ^{ns}	0.59±0.05 ^{ns}	0.24±0.05*	0.16±0.05*

Results of Student's *t* – test **,* – significance at the 0.01, 0.05 probability levels, respectively

NADP-ME is involved in many processes related to plant responses to stress at the metabolic level. Thus, the enzyme plays an important role in maintaining the pH of the cytoplasm stable, regulating the function of the stomatal apparatus, and creating tolerance to stress in plants. Pyruvate, a product of the reaction, is used as a precursor in the biosynthesis of flavinoids and lignin (Sun et al., 2019).

In plants exposed to drought stress, the highest NADP-ME activity was observed in leaves of the Zirva 85 genotype 8 days after irrigation (3.5±0.35 EU/mg protein). In the samples taken from the irrigated variant of the Murov 2 genotype, the activity of the enzyme gradually increased. Significantly lower activity was observed in the leaves of Aran and Gyzyl bughda genotypes compared to the Murov 2 and Zirva 85 genotypes. The results of our experiments confirm the tolerance of the genotypes Murov 2 and Zirva 85 (Table 2).

As a result of the increase in temperature, the upper layer of the soil dries up and osmotic stress occurs around the roots, the concentration of salts and ions that have a toxic effect increases. First of all, this leads to a decrease in the volume and number of leaves (Fathi and Tari, 2016). As a result of stress, RWC in cells and tissues decreases. During drought, due to osmotic adaptation, cells can reduce the osmotic potential and increase the water gradient, maintaining the turgor of the cell by

elasticity. This contributes to maintaining the physiological balance of the plant during long-term drought (Abobatta, 2019). The weakening of the water storage capacity of plants is more pronounced in drought-sensitive genotypes (Kocheva et al 2013). Relative Water Content (RWC) of the leaf, stomatal resistance, transpiration rate, and leaf temperature are important indicators that affect water exchange in the plant. This indicator is high in the early stages of leaf development and decreases when the dry biomass of the plant begins to increase (Amirjani, 2013). The value of RWC in a plant depends on the adsorption of water through the roots and the loss of water through transpiration.

The RWC of the flag leaves of bread wheat genotypes was measured depending on the days of drought in 3 cultivation variants. This parameter was highest in the Murov 2 and Aran genotypes, and lower in the Gyzyl bughda genotype compared to others. In the Murov 2 genotype, RWC remained relatively stable. On the 2nd day of the drought, RWC in the control and stress variants was 90% and 89% and on the 10th day, 85% and 79%, respectively in the Murov 2 genotype (Fig.). In the Aran genotype, RWC at the beginning of the drought was 92% in the control variant and 89% in the stress variant, while on the 10th day of the drought, it amounted to 84% in the control variant and 80% in the stress variant.

Fig. Effect of drought stress on flag leaf relative water content. Each value represents the mean of 3 replicates. Results of Student's *t*-test **, *—significance at the 0.01, 0.05 probability levels, respectively.

On the 4th day of drought, RWC was 89% in the control variant and 88% in the stress variant of the Murov 2 genotype, while in the Gyzyl bughda genotype, this parameter amounted to 73% and 64%, respectively. Thus, the RWC in the Gyzyl bughda genotype was sharply reduced due to the effect of stress. The relative stability of RWC during drought can be explained by a deeper extension of the root system contributing to less osmotic influence, which has been confirmed by our experiments (Marcinińska et al., 2013).

NADP-ME participates in the regeneration process by directing pyruvate and NADPH to the biosynthesis of fatty acids. Stress factors that affect water balance also cause oxidative stress by inducing the regeneration of free oxygen radicals. Drought stress, being one of the most common environmental factors that seriously affect plant development and productivity, causes many physiological, biochemical, and molecular changes in plants.

Furthermore, the results indicated that organic acids such as malate, oxaloacetic acid, citric acid, and fumaric acid play an important role in the primary carbon metabolism in plants. Thus, the research revealed that the Murov 2 genotype can be cultivated in rainfed and semi-arid regions, and can be used as a starting material for creating stress-tolerant wheat varieties in practical breeding programs.

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Yumşaq buğda genotiplərində oksidoreduktaza və dekarboksilaza fəallığına malik malatdehidrogenazaların tədqiqi

Ulduzə Qurbanova

Azərbaycan Respublikası Elm və Təhsil Nazirliyi Molekulyar Biologiya və Biotexnologiyalar İnstitutunun Karbonun fotosintetik assimilyasiyasının enzimologiyası laboratoriyası, Bakı, Azərbaycan

NADP-MDH və NADP-ME-in mühüm və mürəkkəb bir rola malik olması onun ali bitkilərdə karbonun və enerjinin paylanması əhəmiyyətini göstərir. Bu isə bitkilərdə tənəffüs, fotosintez və fototənəffüsü əlaqələndirən biokimyəvi və molekulyar mexanizmlər haqqında yeni ideyaların irəli sürülməsini şərtləndirir. Bu məqsədlə fotosintezin C₃ yoluna aid olan quraqlığa davamlılığına görə fərqlənən yumşaq buğda (*Triticum aestivum* L.) genotiplərinin yarpaqlarında malat metabolizminin əsas fermentləri - NADP-malatdehidrogenaza (NADP-MDH) və NADP-malik enzim (NADP-ME) aktivliyi, nisbi su tutumu (NST) öyrənilmişdir. NADP-MDH ən yüksək fəallıq Murov-2 və Zirvə-85 genotiplərində müşahidə edilmişdir. Murov-2 və Aran genotiplərində NST ən yüksək, Qızıl buğda genotipində isə digərləri ilə müqayisədə aşağı olmuşdur. Aparılmış tədqiqatın nəticələrinə əsasən demək olar ki, Murov-2 genotipi dəmyə və yarım-quraq bölgələrdə becərilməklə yanaşı, seleksiya proqramlarında stresə davamlı buğda sortlarının yaradılmasında ilkin material kimi istifadə oluna bilər.

Açar sözlər: *Quraqlıq stressi, malat metabolizmi, NADP-MDH, NADP-ME*